

Genetic Information Loss as a Consequence of Civilization

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Abstract

There are various well-documented threats that put the long-term survival of humans at risk, such as uncontrolled population growth, air and water pollution, habitat destruction, climate change, artificial intelligence, and weapons of mass destruction. An additional threat that has apparently been overlooked is discussed here. After the dawn of civilization, some of the primeval forces of natural selection that made us what we are ceased to exist. In the long term, this could have profound effects on traits such as vision, hearing, strength, balance, and stamina. This topic is discussed in the context of an underlying population/fitness model and the effects of forcing terms and abrupt changes.

Introduction

Civilization has given rise to various threats that put the long-term survival of humans at risk [1–5]. Some of them are well documented, such as uncontrolled population growth, air and water pollution, habitat destruction, climate change, artificial intelligence, and weapons of mass destruction. An additional threat that has apparently been overlooked is considered here. After the dawn of civilization, some of the primeval forces of natural selection that made us what we are ceased to exist. This change, which was abrupt relative to the time scales over which species evolve, may carry a long-term risk for the human gene pool.

Prior to the dawn of civilization, primeval forces sustained and kept sharp traits such as vision, hearing, strength, balance, and stamina. In the absence of those forces, genes that carry information for such traits would be expected to degrade as a result of random mutations that those forces would have filtered out. Over the course of hundreds of generations, a gradual loss of information from the gene pool could possibly have profound effects. The long-term risk of this process is discussed here in the context of an underlying population/fitness model and the effects of forcing terms and abrupt changes. By making

comparisons between ancient and modern DNA, it might be possible to find evidence for this effect.

Population/Fitness Modeling

Mathematical models are useful for understanding factors that affect the population of a species and the fitness of its gene pool. A simple example is Volterra's prey-predator (such as rabbits and foxes) equations [6],

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = \alpha x - \beta xy, \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{dy}{dt} = -\gamma y + \delta xy, \quad (2)$$

where x is the population density of the prey (which is assumed to have an unlimited food supply), y is the population density of the predator, and the coefficients are related to the birth rate of the prey, the death rate of the predator, and the rate at which the predator succeeds in feeding on the prey. A numerical solution of these equations appears in Fig. 1 for the case $\alpha = 1.2$, $\beta = 1.0$, $\gamma = 2.0$, and $\delta = 1.0$. After each build-up in the population of the prey, the predator benefits from an increased food supply and its population increases (with a slight delay). After the population of the prey is reduced by predation, less food is available to the predator, which suffers a decline in population (also with a slight delay), and the process repeats periodically in this simple model. One way to increase the sophistication of the model would be to allow the coefficients to be time dependent. Appearing in Fig. 2 is a numerical solution for the case in which β and δ increase linearly from 1 to 3 over the interval $0 < t < 40$. This could be representative of a scenario in which the habitat is degrading and affording fewer places for the prey to hide. In this case, the model predicts that both populations decrease as the quality of the habitat decreases.

Another way to increase the sophistication of the model would be to introduce additional dependent variables and allow the coefficients to be functions of the dependent variables, such as in the generalization,

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = \alpha x - \beta(g_x)xy, \quad (3)$$

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Figure 1: Numerical solution of Volterra's prey-predator equations. The population of the predator (dashed curve) is correlated with the population of the prey (solid curve), but with a slight delay.

$$\frac{dy}{dt} = -\gamma y + \delta (g_x) xy, \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{dg_x}{dt} = \epsilon (y, g_x), \quad (5)$$

where the genetic fitness of the prey g_x corresponds to its ability to escape from the predator, the predation success rate depends on g_x , and the rate of change of g_x depends on the population of the predator. Since variations in fitness typically occur over much longer time scales than variations in population, variations in fitness may not become evident in the model until the equations are solved over a long period of time. During a period with a healthy population of predators, which help to keep the gene pool strong, the fitness increases ($\epsilon > 0$), and β and δ decrease. When predators are absent or rare, the fitness decreases ($\epsilon < 0$), and the prey gradually loses the ability to escape from the predator.

Consequences of Abrupt Changes

Although it would be challenging to explicitly formulate a population/fitness model for an ecosystem with many species, the concept of such a model can be a useful framework for understanding the dynamics of such an ecosystem. For each species, the population and the fitnesses associated with various traits would be influenced by relationships with other species. If the ecosystem is in an equilibrium state, an abrupt change could disrupt the balance of the ecosystem and cause it to settle into a new equilibrium state, with some species evolving or going extinct and new species emerging. Following an abrupt change, traits that are no longer influenced

Figure 2: Numerical solution of a modified version of Volterra's prey-predator equations in which the rate at which the predator succeeds in feeding on the prey increases with time. The population of the predator (dashed curve) is correlated with the population of the prey (solid curve), but both populations decrease with time.

by forcing would gradually be lost. The topic of interest here is a specific type of abrupt change and its effects. Before getting to that case, we consider other cases for which abrupt changes are known to have profound effects.

When a predator is introduced into an ecosystem with a prey that has not evolved the ability to escape the predator, the prey may be rapidly driven to extinction, especially if the predator is capable of feeding on other species. When an invasive species is introduced into an ecosystem without predators, its population may initially grow exponentially. After a mass extinction event (e.g., due to a meteor impact), new species may emerge and fill niches that were opened up by the event. There have been many studies about what happens when a species becomes isolated from the habitat in which it evolved after arriving on a remote island (or an isolated patch of habitat on the mainland) [7–11], where it may adapt to a more limited range (in terms of area) or gradually split into multiple species that fill different niches on the island. Changes in the environment during an ice age can have profound effects [12–14]. Populations of a species that are isolated from each other by glaciers may evolve into separate species. Natural selection may cause an avian species to lose migratory behavior during the ice age and then regain it after the ice recedes.

Prior to the dawn of civilization, having exceptional eyesight, hearing, and other physical traits would be an advantage for finding prey and escaping from predators. After suspending some of the primeval forces that maintained such traits, random mutations would be expected to result in the weak-

ening of such traits through the gradual loss of genetic information. In terms of an underlying population/fitness model, this type of abrupt change would seem to be comparable in magnitude to some of those mentioned above. Indeed, civilization has had profound and well-studied effects on the environment and other species, but its effects on the human population itself and the potential risk for diminished senses and other traits have apparently been overlooked. If the human gene pool has been gradually losing information for thousands of years, it might be possible to find evidence for this process by making comparisons between modern and ancient human DNA, such as from the Tyrolean Ice Man, who died in (and was preserved in) a glacier in the Alps about 5300 years ago [15]. Many viable samples of DNA from several hundred years ago are available; for example, a study of immune genes was based on DNA samples (including 360 with “sufficient endogenous DNA for downstream enrichment and sequencing”) from populations before, during, and after the Black Death in 1348 and 1349 [16].

DNA from different human populations that became civilized at different times and have been genetically isolated from each other might contain evidence for information loss, which might be more advanced for the population that became civilized earlier. Another possible source of evidence for information loss is long-term medical statistics related to vision, hearing, and other traits (but perhaps not until a longer record becomes available well into the future). On the basis of what is known about the rate of random mutations, it might be possible to estimate the number of generations that would be required for the effects of information loss to become noticeable in humans. Making DNA comparisons between domestic animals and their wild counterparts [17–19] may provide insights into this process.

Civilization would not be expected to bring an end to all types of natural selection in humans. Natural selection for fertility may not have been impacted by civilization until the advent of fertility treatments in recent decades. Natural selection for the immune system may not have been impacted by civilization until the advent of vaccines in the 20th Century; in fact, there exists evidence that the evolution of human immunity was influenced by the Black Death [16], which occurred thousands of years after the dawn of civilization. Although gradual dulling of certain traits might occur in a civilized population, random mutations that cause serious defects would still be filtered out. Different traits would be favored in a civilized population; for example, vision, hearing, and other physical traits might be dulled, while traits that favor success in a civilized population are enhanced.

Discussion

Considering that the survival of early humans depended on relationships with other species as both predator and prey, the human gene pool must have been molded by primeval forces of natural selection that favored sharp senses and robust physical traits. Some of those forces ceased to exist after the dawn of civilization, and the process of losing information from the gene pool through random mutations would presumably have started dulling some of the traits of early humans. Basic survival-related traits would no longer be vital, while a new set of forces of natural selection would favor traits that are useful in a civilized population. It might be possible to find evidence for information loss by making comparisons between ancient and modern DNA. If some of the traits of early humans are indeed gradually being lost or dulled, this process could put our long-term survival at risk, at least in our present form.

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